

CONFIRMATION OF AN AMPHIBIAN SPECIES, ASIAN COMMON TOAD (*Duttaphrynus melanostictus*), FROM ST. MARTIN'S ISLAND OF BAY OF BENGAL

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation was on an amphibian species in St. Martin's Island, far from main land and isolated by sea water. The collected individuals were normal and the taxonomic parameters were more or less similar to the main land individuals. Important parameters were on an average - Snout to Vent Length, 57.4 mm (SD± 3.40049 mm; head length, 24.97143 mm (SD± 3.690399 mm); head width, 20.41429 mm (SD± 3.411465); inter-orbital distance, 7.9 mm (SD± 0.955685 mm); diameter of tympanum, 3.771429 mm (SD± 0.675066 mm); distance between tympanum and eye, 1.5 mm (SD± 0.244949 mm). All the taxonomic parameters were positively co-related with snout to vent length. Wart pattern on the skin are different in each individual. This scenario can be hypothetically linked to the intensification of climate dynamic or to probable intra or interspecific competition.

Key words: *Duttaphrynus melanostictus*, St. Martin's Island, saline condition, taxonomic parameters.

Introduction

Amphibians are particularly sensitive because they are generally poor osmoregulators, and most species are completely absent from brackish and saline environments (Gomez-Mestre *et al.*, 2004). Though few toad species are capable of breeding in saline condition (Gomez-Mestre and Tejedo, 2004) but it is very rare case to inhabit in such condition. Amphibians thrive best in regimes of 20-30°C and thus their geographic distribution is very limited (Duellmen and Trueb, 1986). Even if these species acclimated to saline conditions for a while they must change their physiology (Gomez-Mestre *et al.*, 2004), histology and shift stages of metamorphosis (Uchiyama and Yoshizawa, 1992). *Duttaphrynus melanostictus* is very common in Bangladesh (Rahman *et al.*, 2011). It is reported that this species is habituated to human dominated ecosystems. They are even uncommon in closed forests, far from human populated areas (IUCN, 2012). Though Bangladesh is considered of being a global biodiversity hotspot in tropical Asia and having a unique and highly threatened biota (Encyclopedia of Flora and Fauna of Bangladesh, 2009), unfortunately, the status and distribution of amphibians has not evaluated yet with any in-depth study or survey (Chowdhury, 1996; Khan, 2008). St. Martin's Island is a small piece of land surrounded by marine water; it is very significant to find a toad species there. It could be an entrance point for further study on amphibian in saline ecosystem. Hence the present study was designed with a view to investigate the body structures of the identified amphibian (Asian common toad) and evaluated with the species habituated in human dominated ecosystems.

Materials and Methods

The survey was conducted during September, 2012 to January, 2013 in the St. Martin's island with N 20° 37' 57.04" latitude and E 92° 19' 11.80" longitude (Map 1). It is a small island in the northeastern part of the Bay of Bengal, about 9 km south of the tip of the Cox's Bazar-Teknaf peninsula, and forming the southernmost part of Bangladesh. The local name of the island is "Narical Gingira" translated from Bangla, meaning 'Coconut Island'. It is the only coral island in Bangladesh. A small adjoining island that is separated at high tide, called "Chhera" island. It is about 8 km west of the northwest coast of Myanmar, at the mouth of the Naf River. 1st settlement started just 250 years ago by some Arabian Sailors and named as 'Zajira'. During British occupation the island was named as St. Martin Island. The local name of the island is "Narical Gingira", meaning 'Coconut Island' and in Bengali literature it is known as "Daruchini Dip" (District Gazetteer, 1976). It is the only coral island in Bangladesh. During the high tide this island is shrinking to about 5 km² (2 sq. mi). The island exists only because of its coral base, so degeneration of coral reefs is risked erosion of the beaches.

Map 1 St. Martyn's Island

The specimens were collected from different parts of the St. Martin's island. The random searching method was applied for the collection. Collections of specimen were mainly done in the evening up to midnight as amphibians are nocturnal in behavior. Hand picking was main method to catch them but sometimes different nets were used too. The specimens were searched thoroughly everywhere of St. Martin's Island but different corners of local households and surroundings of the temporary or permanent water were get most priority. Light traps at night also used to catch them. A total of 27 mature and 12 immature specimens were collected of which 18 were male and 21 female. The date, time, place of collection, habitat type, color, and individual no. were recorded immediate after collection with a tag in bottle and plastic and glass zars. Some photographs were also taken for clear justification of the study. These specimens were killed by chloroform and preserved in either 5-10% formalin.

The specimens were identified through cross-matching images from different books and websites. Sometimes expertise supports also taken from proficient. The taxonomic keys were studied to ensure their identity. The important keys were- Dorsal fold, Longitudinal fold, Supra-tympanic, Dorsal color, Ventral color, Head length (HL), Head width (HW), Inter-orbital width (IOD), Diameter of tympanum (TYD), Diameter of tympanum from eye (DBET), Snout to vent length (SVL), Relative study of toe, Relative study of finger, Degree of webbing, Pupil shape, Tongue shape, Vomarine teeth, Overlapping of hind limb, Tibio-tarsus articulation, Discs of digits, Parotid gland and Warts on the body.

Methods of Data Analysis: Standard deviation, range and correlation coefficient were measured for data analysis. A range defines the normal limits of a biological characteristic (Mahajan, 1997). Range can be measured as- $R = X_{(n)} - X_{(1)}$; $X_{(n)}$ = The lowest observation in the series and $X_{(1)}$ = The highest observation in the series (Bhuyan, 2004).

Standard deviation was calculated to observe the variation of difference of an observation from the mean is by chance or real due to special reason. Basically it is used to know the precision of estimate (Bhuyan, 2004). It can be measured as-

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2}, \quad \text{where } \mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i.$$

The extent of degree or relationship between two sets of figures is measured through correlation coefficient as stated by Mahajan, 1997. It was calculated according to the following formula

$$r = \frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Result and Discussion

Observations of identifying characters: The skin was full of warts (Photo 1). Wart pattern were different in each individual. This observation suggests the accuracy of identification method of Duellman and Trueb, 1994. Dorsal folds and longitudinal folds were absent, instead a pair of parotid glands were present; supra-tympanic prominent; relative length of fingers were $3 > 4 > 1 > 2$ and toes were $4 > 5 = 3 > 2 > 1$; webbing pattern was rudimentary; pupil was horizontal whereas tongue was round shaped; vomerine teeth and discs on digits were absent; hind limbs were not overlapped; tibio-tarsus articulation reached up to the tympanum. These results were also observed in inland specimens (Rahman *et al*, 2011; Daniel, 2002).

***Photographed by the first author**

Photo 1 *Duttaphrynus melanostictus* from St. Martyn's Island

Size: Average size of the specimens i.e., Snout to Vent Length (SVL) were 57.4 mm (SD± 3.40049 mm; Range from 48.2 mm to 59.5 mm, n=27; only adults), more or less similar to other parts of Bangladesh (Rahman *et al*, 2011) and the world (Daniel, 2002).

Color: All the specimens of this species were greyish dorsally and whitish ventrally (n=27, only adults), but the immature were with reddish upper side. Rahman *et al*, (2011) and Boulenger (1980) also described same colorations.

Measurements of taxonomic parameters: All the taxonomic parameters (Table 1) were positively co-related with snout to vent length (HL 0.995418, HW 0.967474, IOD 0.668247, TYD 0.920619 and DBET 0.920619) and were very close to Rahman *et al*, (2011).

Table 1 : Measurements of different taxonomic parameters found in Asian Common Toad, *Duttaphrynus melanostictus*, collected from St. Martyn's Island

Identifying key	Average (mm)	Range (mm)	Standard Deviation
SVL	57.4	48.2 to 59.5	± 3.40049
HL	24.97143	19.7 to 29.5	± 3.690399
HW	20.41429	16 to 24.3	± 3.411465
IOD	7.9	8.1 to 9.2	± 0.955685
TYD	3.771429	3 to 5	± 0.675066
DBET	1.5	1.3 to 2	± 0.244949

(NB : SVL=Snout to Vent Length; HL=Head Length; HW=Head Width; IOD=Inter Orbital Distance; TYD=Diameter of Tympanum; DBET=Distance Between Eye and Tympanum.)

An analysis of the situation

D. melanostictus is the first amphibian species reported from St. Martin's Island in Bay of Bengal. It was supposed to be an extremely inhabitant of terrestrial and freshwater ecosystem (IUCN, 2012), but contrastingly two individuals were collected from even less than 200 meters from the sea during the present study. Though it is not the first report of having saline tolerant race of a toad species (Gomez-Mestre and Tejedo, 2004), but first of its kind being reported from 100% saline water isolated island, from where there was no previous record of presence of any amphibian species till date.

Though the specimens were collected mainly from or near local households, markets and hotels, there are many important questions to be answered. How the first individual landed here? If somehow one has come then what about his or her mating partner? It is tough to believe that they travelled to the island by themselves as they have very limited move ability. But there is a great chance of being transported through ship or boat. Then the most important question arises, why they would do this? Why they risked their life? If they did so, they had to pass through an overcrowded environment and up to some distance of sea water. Only the hypotheses of intensification of climate dynamic and probable intra or inter specific competition can minimize all these questions up to a certain level.

Though genetic tests are wanting, it is an amazing finding that any amphibian species can be found in a salt water isolated island and can healthily maintain their life-cycle. Finding these specimens in odd season is another mystery of this studies which yet to be solved. As perspectives opened up by this work, more research is required in order to establish the relationship of *D. melanostictus* in freshwater with marine water species; also, a revision of *D. melanostictus* record in Bangladesh is needed in order to clarify whether there were no, one or two dispersal events for Asian toads in St. Martin's Island.

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